

A HYBRID APPROACH FOR OPTIMAL POWER USAGE SCHEDULING IN SMART GRID MANAGEMENT USING RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND DEMAND RESPONSE

JUNAID MIRAJ

Department of Electrical Engineering, CECOS University of Information Technology & Emerging Sciences, Peshawar, Pakistan.

KHALID REHMAN *

Department of Electrical Engineering, CECOS University of Information Technology & Emerging Sciences, Peshawar, Pakistan. *Corresponding Author Email: khalid@cecos.edu.pk, sahibzadaan@gmail.com

MAZHAR ALI

Department of Electrical Engineering, CECOS University of Information Technology & Emerging Sciences, Peshawar, Pakistan.

Abstract

DSM, or demand side management, is vital for the efficiency of smart grids. Since it reduces Electricity Costs (EC), and Home energy management systems, or HEMSs, are quickly emerging as essential instruments for maximizing family energy use. In this research, we propose a unique technique for appliance scheduling in residential settings that minimizes costs and ensures optimal delay: The Genetic Flower Pollination Algorithm (GFPA). The GFPA algorithm presented here is a hybrid method that integrates Flower Pollination Algorithm (FPA) and Genetic Algorithm (GA) components. By use of optimum scheduling patterns, our GFPA technique aims to simultaneously maximize User Comfort (UC) and minimize EC and PAR, having undergone rigorous testing at multiple sizes ranging from individual homes to bigger communities. Assuming stability in the types of appliances and patterns of power usage Simulation findings indicate that the GFPA technique improves the existing methods across households. To achieve optimal power scheduling, this research integrates demand response mechanisms and renewable energy sources into a new hybrid technique for smart grid management. It highlights how careful research and testing may improve grid dependability, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness. Through resolving current energy system issues and developing smart grid technologies, this research offers significant perspectives for developing a more dependable and effective energy future.

Index Terms: Smart Grid; Demand Side Management; Home Energy Management System; Renewable Energy Source; Genetic Algorithm; Flower Pollination Algorithm; Heuristic Algorithms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Use of the smart grid technology, nowadays, it is possible to integrate the most advanced power grid infrastructure with extensive interactive monitoring and control capabilities. Demand response and renewable energy sources are becoming more and more visible, which opens up new possibilities for effective energy management. When RES and DR are combined, an efficient method to schedule power use in smart grids is produced, which may reduce environmental effects, increase dependability, and save costs. The huge rise in energy consumption means that the traditional grid cannot keep up with the demands of the modern world. The concept of the smart grid was developed as a result

of the previous grid's low efficiency and many upkeep and reliability problems. The development of communication technologies and their integration with the electrical infrastructure has transformed the traditional grid into a smart grid. This hybrid approach resulted from research on demand response techniques and renewable energy sources used in combination for smart grid control. The research is clearly relevant since it addresses the following issues. Two of the biggest problems facing modern power networks are the erratic behavior of renewable energy sources and changing demand patterns. The proposed technique maximizes energy consumption while preserving grid consistency and reliability by combining RES and DR into a single, integrated design. The chapter starts with an overview of modern smart grid technologies and how they integrate with renewable energy sources and demand response. Next, the chapter outlines research goals, particular study desired outcomes, and contributions. A thorough explanation of the research methodology which includes the hybrid strategy utilized to properly plan the usage of power footsteps. It provides as a foundation for further investigation into potential methods of combining renewable energy sources as well as demand response technologies to increase both the efficiency and the sustainability of smart grid management. Through careful examination and testing, the project's goal is to show that the suggested hybrid strategy is both practical and successful, offering crucial data for the future development and use of smart grid technologies.

2. RELATED WORK

Many studies are being undertaken to enhance energy management in the area of smart grids through the scheduling of Automatically Operated Appliances (AOAs). Modern electrical technology has increased consumer energy demands and changed the energy system as a whole. First available plug-in hybrid electric vehicles have been identified in [9]. There are two easily accessible ways to meet user demand: either generation companies must expand their capacity by building new power plants, or they can better manage energy by scheduling consumer appliances. The first approach is more expensive since it necessitates large expenditures to boost production capacity by adding new power plants in parallel with the current ones. This will also make the grid's power transmission and distribution system more complex. Compared to the second strategy merely needs to introduce various price strategies for different periods of the day in order to manage the current demand. For example, in [10], the method known as Direct Load Control (DLC) is explained. The utility employs the DLC technique that encourages consumers to move their load from peak to off-peak hours and use less energy during peak hours, to lower demand [11]. [12]. In order to prevent peaks from forming during off-peak times, an inclining block rate (IBR) is included in addition to TOU and RTP. The HEMS algorithm is shown in [13], which lowers energy consumption and electricity costs by allocating appliances based on TOU price parameters. Controllable appliances are monitored, scheduled, and controlled by HEMS [14]. By allocating specific timeslots for every device, Home Energy Management Systems (HEMS) lower PAR. The utility sends out different pricing signals that determine when automatic appliances should run [23].

But many articles give a sufficient amount of time for each equipment, which isn't practical for certain appliances like blenders, kettles, and juicers. Even if [5] addresses the drawback of the extended time period, user comfort was compromised. The formulation of user comfort is carried out in [4], which considers the reduction of energy and appliance waiting times. An in-depth review was conducted, where a number of highly reliable algorithms were covered. If someone wishes to reduce power usage, there is also the matter of user comfort [22]. The reality that these research efforts do not integrate that One of the main disadvantages of the smart grid is its use of renewable energy sources. In the modern world, it is hard to imagine an electrical power system without including renewable energy sources (RESs) [14]. The authors [15] present MINLP, which uses RTP to schedule thermal and electrical appliances to reduce energy usage thus reducing energy expenses and enhancing user comfort. Although the performance was fairly effective across several models, this technique's high computational cost is a downside. The user's changes to the appliance schedule were taken into account by the authors in [16]; nevertheless, the requirements for implementing the changes had to be met the following day, which raised customer dissatisfaction. This issue was resolved by the authors in [1], allowing the user to request the switching of one appliance for another while keeping the other one running. The authors in [17] looked at energy storage systems that use scheduling to cut peak demand and power costs by nearly a fifth using linear programming. Three goals were addressed in [18] using the Evolutionary Algorithm (EA): lowering the cost of electricity, minimizing carbon dioxide emissions while increasing power consumption. Distributed generation (DG) was used by the authors of [19] to enable bidirectional power transmission, reducing the amount of time appliances had to wait and lowering energy costs [26]. The costs associated with installation, upkeep, and operation, however, were entirely disregarded. [20] And [21] discuss how to use linear programming (LP) and evolutionary accounting (EA) to reduce peak demand and electricity costs, respectively.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The popularity of electric automobiles, the growth of industry, and developments in technology have all contributed to an important rise in global power consumption during the past several decades. By 2040, energy use is expected to have increased. Old power systems manage to keep up with the increasing demands of the modern world because of their inefficiency, dependability problems, and maintenance needs. These issues can be effectively solved with smart grids, which are made feasible by advancements in communication technologies. By means of incentive-based systems, utilities are able to exert control over the energy consumption patterns of their customers and allow two-way communication networks. Although smart grids have numerous advantages, it is still difficult to maintain supply and demand patterns while effectively managing energy usage, even with developments in management of assets, durability, and consumer satisfaction Demand-side management and home energy management systems (HEMS) are becoming important parts of energy management methods for smart grids because of

their capacity to optimize load scheduling and reduce peak demand. The current DSM and HEMS approaches to implementation have drawbacks and need more research to fully realize their capacity to improve grid reliability and effectiveness. In besides creating new challenges, including renewable energy sources (RES) into smart grid management presents chances to enhance energy management and demand response techniques. By applying advanced modeling techniques and real-time data analysis, the proposed model aims to improve load scheduling, balance supply and demand, and increase grid resilience in the face of increasing energy demand and renewable energy integration. Long-term, our research aims to support the development of affordable, efficient, and environmentally friendly energy sources that can adjust to the demands of modern society.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

A Heuristic method for energy management issue solutions are proposed. The scheduling problem cannot be properly solved by the methods now in use in order to accomplish energy management. When it comes to tackling the scheduling problem for appliances, the majority of these algorithms are computationally complicated, and as the number of appliances rises, their efficiency falls. The majority of techniques also do not take appliance coordination into account. In order to overcome the aforementioned constraints in scheduling problem solution, a hybrid algorithm called GFPA. There are four main steps in the process of generating, distributing, transmitting, and consuming electricity. There are more categories for consumption: business, residential, and industrial. Numerous In the literature, optimization techniques have been suggested for Demand-Side Management (DSM). The Genetic Flower -Pollination Algorithm (GFPA), which is suggested in this study, lowers Energy Consumption (EC) by scheduling appliances. Combining the Flower Algorithm (FPA) and Genetic Algorithm (GA), GFPA makes it easier to find the best solutions when resources are limited. The GA and FPA are combined to create the hybrid technique known as GFPA. These methods facilitate the process of selecting the best and most appropriate option from among all those that could be achieved with the available resources.

Figure 1: Proposed system model

5. METHODOLOGY

Both the Flower Pollination Algorithm (FPA) and the Genetic Algorithm (GA), together known as the GFPA technology, are combined in the suggested methodology for optimizing Smart grids with demand-side management (DSM). John Holland created the Genetic Algorithm in the 1970s, and it works by keeping track of a population of possible answers, symbolized by chromosomes. It is suitable for optimizing appliance scheduling to reduce the PAR, or peak-to-average ratio and minimize DSM costs in smart grids since it iteratively evolves towards an optimal solution. The Flower Pollination Algorithm, on the other hand, has become well-known for its ability to solve a variety of optimization issues by simulating the pollination process of flowering plants. Because it generates solutions that work, FPA is a key component of the suggested scheduling strategy for DSM in smart grids. We are utilizing the GFPA approach to combine the greatest aspects of both worlds. It's similar to combining the strengths of two effective technologies, GA and FPA, to further improve the optimization process. The crossover and mutation characteristics from GA are what we're using; they're like the secret sauce for improving outcomes. While crossover facilitates the mixing and matching of various components of solutions, mutation adds some flavor by introducing variation. The GFPA algorithm provides a completely new way for scheduling optimization in smart grids by combining these techniques. It's revolutionary for efficient and superior demand-side management systems.

Figure 2: Overview of smart Grid

6. RESULTS

In this section, we examine the simulation's outcomes and the relevant discussions in an effort to demonstrate the efficiency and efficacy of our efforts in achieving flawless smart home scheduling. Scheduling scenarios for scalable communities with 10–50 homes are included in the models that are run. The efficient allocation of Appliance use is ensured by the scheduling algorithms between peak and off-peak hours, which efficiently regulate energy management. When scheduling numerous residences with comparable appliances but varying Priority Rates (PRs), real-time scenarios are taken into consideration. Every appliance is given a random PR in order to simulate real-world circumstances. The power ratings of the various appliance types used in the present research are displayed table 1. Given that many appliances fall into the range of appliance types covered in this thesis's third chapter. The simulation results show how well Flower Pollination Algorithm (FPA), Genetic Algorithm (GA), and our hybrid approach—GFPA—perform at various time scales and house counts. Notably, GFPA constantly performs better than the alternative methods, demonstrating notable cost savings, improvements in User Comfort and rises in user comfort and the Peak-to-Average Ratio (PAR).

Table 1: 'Appliance With power Ratings

Home Appliances	Power Rating (Watts)	Home Appliances	Power Rating (Watts)
Air Conditioner	70-130	Juicer Blender	200
Refrigerator	70-100	Vacuum Cleaner	50-120
Washing Machine	100	EV/ESS	250

• **PAR Minimization:**

The simulation shown in the graph intends to reduce the smart grid system's peak-to-average ratio (PAR). The link between average and peak power consumption is represented by PAR, which is essential for effective grid management. The y-axis displays electricity generation or demand in kilowatts (kW), while the x-axis represents time periods ranging from hours to months. The power profile is represented by the plotted line, while times of high or low demand is indicated by variations and smoother curves, which show usage continuously. In ensuring not overloading infrastructure of grid, aim of lowering RAP is to even those spikes in power consumption. By adjusting our power scheduling, put demand response strategies into place, and ensuring utilizing renewable energy sources as effectively as possible, can do this. Simulation is demonstrating how successful RAP reduction may be in reducing grid demand and maximizing resources available. This assists in saving money and preserving environment in addition to relieving some strain of grid.

Figure 3: PAR Minimization

• **Cost Reduction:**

Reducing the ratio of peak to average (PRA) are strongly associated with the primary goal of that research, which is to reduce cost in the end, this provides financial benefits to everyone. A highest PRA indicates that they are used the costly Peak power plants during

peak hours, that raising the prices of electricity. This study aims to demonstrate how lowering PRA may results in saving costs for power providers and customers. The emphasis is on implementing solution like require response programs, scheduling optimization, and the use of surplus renewable power sources in order to achieve this. Through less sudden growths in power demands, these strives hope to minimize the needs for costly pinn65acle power plants and enhance operational efficiency.

Figure 4: Cost Reduction

- **Limiting Carbon Emission**

As traditional power plants that use fossil fuels like coal are the primary source of environmental pollution, reducing carbon emissions is of greatest importance. In order to address air pollution and climate change, this research highlights the use of sustainable energy techniques. Carbon capture systems are being deployed, along with the benefit of more sustainable energy sources. Including renewable energy sources, such wind and solar power, reduces greenhouse gas emissions while also enhancing energy efficiency. The decrease in carbon emissions that these actions achieve is measured by environmental impact assessments, which are carried out in line with more general sustainability objectives of lowering dependency on fossil fuels and lessening the consequences of climate change.

Figure 5: Carbon Emission Limitation simulation

- **User Comfort Maximization**

The research aims at optimizing power consumption efficacy through the strategic location of electrical gear to upgrade user comfort and happiness. Through cautious regulation of appliance operation, the research looks to offer customers greater flexibility, convenience, and mastery over how much power they utilize. This will secure that electric resources are utilized as efficiently as likely. The plan looks to enrich appliance scheduling consistent with customer choices, energy rates, and grid situations by employing multiple strategies. This includes deciding when appliances should be utilized to maximize customer contentment, decrease energy costs, and diminish grid overcrowding all at the same moment.

Figure 6: User comfort Maximization Simulation

- **Coordination among Appliances**

Smart grid to enhance energy and increase system endurance, gadgets must operate along as an inconsistent unit. The actuality that unproductive coordination could result in inefficiencies, expanded energy usage, and pressure on the grid stresses the necessity of discovering a resolution. The creation of schemes for improved grid-to-client and gadget-to-gadget coordination is the aspiration of this venture. Different strategies are implemented to accomplish this. Primarily, gadgets may interact and cooperate with each other utilizing technologies like Wi-Fi by considering user predilections and current grid circumstances. Additionally, optimizing energy effectiveness and decreasing grid stress throughout peak periods are the aims of blending request reaction and gadget coordinating schemes. Lastly, it's more facile to coordinate when examining clever home automation alternatives gadgets in alignment with timetables and energy-conserving requisites. By evaluating gadget patterns of usage, coordination policies are further enhanced through the use of modeling and machinery learning. Improving grid-consumer interaction also aids in grid optimization initiatives by furnishing users with the latest information on request reaction events, system circumstances, and electricity price. This aids consumers in making precise determinations concerning how much energy to utilize, which boosts the grid's overall dependability and effectiveness.

Figure 7: Coordination among Appliances

7. CONCLUSION

Our simulation results, in summary, highlight the significance that improved scheduling algorithms play in enabling sustainable and reasonably priced smart home management. Our results demonstrate how different scheduling methods can be employed in practice to improve energy efficiency while offsetting peak time problems. Our simulations demonstrate that our algorithms can effectively allocate appliances over peak and off-

peak times and program conditions over a variety of community sizes. By assigning each appliance a random Priority Rate, we sought to replicate actual life scenario to increase the relevancy and applicability of our findings. Given that all other scheduling methods assessed, including the Genetic Algorithm and the House, performed better than our hybrid strategy, known as GFPA. This is significant for the Flower Pollination Algorithm (FPA) and for several time periods. It was demonstrated that GFPA performed better from the peak-to-average ratio (PAR) perspective, user comfort (UC), and significant cost savings. Based on our research, we have identified three key areas where these scheduling strategies may significantly improve performance. Initially, our simulations demonstrated how scheduling techniques may reduce the peak-to-average ratio (PAR) and assist achieve more balanced power demand patterns. This might lessen the strain on the grid infrastructure and enhance reliability, cost-effectiveness, and environmental sustainability. Second, there was a clear link between minimizing PAR and cutting costs; a lower PAR results in less reliance on expensive peak power plants, which eventually saves money for consumers and power companies alike. Finally, our study underlined the significance of reducing carbon emissions from traditional power plants and the part that efficient scheduling algorithms play in coordinating with more general sustainability objectives in conclusion, our research highlights the fact that effective scheduling algorithms not only maximize energy consumption but also help to improve overall sustainability, grid reliability, and climate change mitigation. Adopting these sophisticated scheduling techniques will be crucial to maximizing the potential of smart home technologies as we move closer to a more intelligent and environmentally friendly future.

8. FUTURE WORK

The following directions could be explored by expanding this study work in the future.

1. A fog and cloud-based technology will be used in the smart grid for better energy management.
2. Utility and customer collaboration for load scheduling will be used in order to reduce energy waste.
3. There will be a two-way power exchange between the utility and the customers that takes grid-to-vehicle and vehicle-to-grid energy optimization into account. We will present a Lyapunov optimization algorithm for online and real-time energy optimization that considers both consumer and utility on-site requests.

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